

AREE FORESTALI DI INFILTRAZIONE PER LA DENITRIFICAZIONE DI ACQUE INQUINATE DA NITRATI

Forested Infiltration Areas for the denitrification of water polluted by nitrates

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Sommario

Una tecnica MAR (Managed Aquifer Recharge) è applicata sotto forma di Area Forestale di Infiltrazione (AFI) per ridurre la contaminazione da nitrati in un acquifero situato in una Zona Vulnerabile da Nitrati (ZVN). La tecnica AFI è implementata in un sito pilota la cui falda presenta una concentrazione media di nitrati di 45 mg L⁻¹, ai limiti del valore soglia fissato dalla normativa (50 mg L⁻¹). Nell'area viene immessa acqua di drenaggio prelevata da una adiacente idrovora, caratterizzata da una concentrazione media di nitrati di 70 mg L⁻¹. L'infiltrazione avviene in sei trincee di ricarica lunghe complessivamente 290 m, profonde un metro e riempite con una miscela omogenea di cippato di eucalipto (50% in volume), materiale inerte (ghiaia e sabbia), argilla e ossidi di ferro. Questa miscela, denominata "Passive Treatment System" (PTS), favorirà l'azione dei batteri denitrificanti che riducono il nitrato (NO₃⁻) in azoto atmosferico (N₂). Si prevede quindi di abbattere i nitrati nell'acqua di drenaggio immessa nelle trincee, utilizzando successivamente la stessa acqua per ricaricare e diluire la falda sottostante inquinata. I risultati preliminari del monitoraggio idrogeochimico mostrano un'apprezzabile riduzione di NO₃⁻ nell'acqua di infiltrazione, dimostrando che la tecnica AFI può essere un'efficace Nature Based Solution per la decontaminazione di acque inquinate da nitrati.

Abstract

A Managed Aquifer Recharge technique is applied in the Forested Infiltration Area's (FIA) form to reduce the nitrogen contamination in an aquifer located in an area falling within a Nitrate Vulnerable Zone (NVZ). The FIA technique is applied in a pilot site whose groundwater has an average concentration of nitrates of 45 mg L^{-1} , close to the threshold value (50 mg L^{-1}). The system delivers drainage water taken from a near-dewatering pump, characterized by an average concentration of nitrates of 70 mg L^{-1} . Infiltration occurs in six recharge trenches with a total length of 290 m, one meter deep and filled with a homogeneous mixture of Eucalyptus wood chips (50% of volume), inert material (gravel and sand), clay and iron oxides. The mixture, named "Passive Treatment System" (PTS), will promote the action of denitrifying bacteria, that converts nitrate (NO_3^-) into atmospheric nitrogen (N_2). Consequently, a reduction in nitrates concentration is anticipated in the drainage water discharged in the trenches, to subsequently utilize the same water for recharging and diluting the underlying polluted groundwater. Preliminary results of hydrogeochemical monitoring indicate a significant reduction of nitrates in the infiltration water, affirming the effectiveness of the FIA technique as a Nature-Based Solution for decontaminating water polluted by nitrates.

1. Introduction

Groundwater pollution by nitrate (NO_3^-) is a global issue that has been known for years. Nitrate groundwater contamination primarily stems from anthropogenic sources (Della Rocca et al., 2005). Mitigating NO_3^- in groundwater is crucial, and denitrification emerges as a pivotal process in this context (Grau-Martínez et al., 2017). Denitrification occurs ubiquitously in soil, groundwater, and surface water under anaerobic conditions, and involves microorganisms utilizing NO_3^- as a terminal electron acceptor, converting it into N_2 (Zhong et al., 2020). An additional consideration in monitoring these processes is the potential production of greenhouse gases, such as nitrous oxide (N_2O).

Managed aquifer recharge (MAR) is a technique to increase water supplies through the realization of basins, furrows, ditches, or ponds where surface water is allowed to flow or accumulate. Implementing these systems on a field scale is possible through the implementation of Forested Infiltration Areas (FIAs), a specialized MAR approach that involves the distribution of water within an appropriately designed area. This area features dispersing channels or trenches lined with a tree system comprising one or more tree or shrub species (Mezzalana et al., 2014). While tree roots in FIAs promote and maximize water infiltration rate, tree roots in symbiosis with microorganisms of soil can play a crucial role in NO_3^- attenuation. Grau-Martínez et al., (2017) demonstrated how Permeable Reactive Barriers (PRBs), such as an organic substrate layer can exhibit notable phytoremediation function. Coupling FIAs with PRBs at the bottom of the recharge trenches can have a significant effect on reducing NO_3^- . Introducing water with a high NO_3^- content into the FIA where water undertook decontamination can enhance the quality of the underlying groundwater through the infiltration of improved water quality (Carletti et al., 2020).

The general objective of this study was to implement an innovative and sustainable Nature-Based Solution (NBS) to address NO_3^- pollution in aquifers. Specifically, our focus was on assessing the potential denitrification efficacy of the FIA technique within a Nitrate Vulnerable Zone (NVZ) in Sardinia Island, Italy.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Study site

The experiment was conducted in the Forested Infiltration Area established in the Arborea district (Sardinia, Italy) (3 m a.s.l., 39°43'01" N, 8°33'25" E). This expansive plain, spanning approximately 60 km², currently stands as the most productive area in Sardinia for agriculture and dairy cattle farming (Demurtas et al., 2016). Significantly, a substantial portion of this area was designated as NVZ in 2005, thereby subjecting it to the regulatory provisions outlined in the European Directive 91/676/EEC prescriptions.

2.2 Experimental setup

The FIA system was established in an approximately 0.4-hectare area, comprising six parallel recharge trenches placed between rows of *Eucalyptus*, *Populus alba* and *Populus nigra*. The recharge trenches, with a total length of 290 meters, were excavated to a depth of one meter and feature an inverted trapezoidal section, with the smaller base measuring 0.50 m and the larger base 1.50 m. The six trenches were connected to form a closed system and were filled to 0.80 m starting from the bottom with a Passive Treatment System (PTS) installed between two beds of medium-coarse gravel (particle size between 4 and 16 mm), with a thickness of 0.10 meters, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1 – View of the Forested Infiltration Area (FIA) of Arborea (OR)

In the FIA study area were implemented an arboreal plant of 180 trees which included *Eucalyptus*, *Populus alba* and *Populus nigra* species. The aim was to promote the symbiotic relationships between microorganisms of soil and roots and facilitate the decontamination process within the FIA system. Furthermore, in early root stages when the tree roots are not developed a PTS was introduced to promote the denitrification process until the tree roots are sufficiently established. The PTS filling material within the trenches is composed of:

1. Inert material, including gravel and sand, constituting 50% of the mixture's volume. This material provides structural integrity and ensures adequate hydraulic conductivity.
2. *Eucalyptus* woodchips, constituting 49% of the mixture's volume.
3. Minor clays ($\leq 1\%$ by volume), primarily consisting of non-expansive illite, offering sites for adsorption of cationic organic contaminants.
4. Iron oxides ($\leq 0.1\%$ by volume), providing sites for adsorption of anionic organic contaminants.

The FIA system was designed to receive low-quality drainage water with a NO_3^- concentration ranging from 40 to 70 mg L^{-1} sourced from the supply system located within the dewatering pumping station of Luri (Idrovora di Luri). This supply system is equipped with two horizontal submersible pumps, each boasting a power of 5.5 kW. The drainage water undergoes filtration before being channeled into the FIA to preserve the infiltration rate and prevent clogging. The supply pipeline, branching off from the filtration system, delivers water to the six parallel recharge trenches within the experimental plot.

2.3 Water analyses

The efficacy of the FIA system in mitigating NO_3^- pollution was assessed through a set of monitoring tools. Groundwater sampling was conducted through five piezometers, Pz, that were drilled at a depth of 5 m within the FIA plot (see Figure 1), and one at a depth of 9 m outside the FIA designated area. Water samplings were conducted once a week for chemical analyses. Various sampling points were designated, and analyses were conducted both in the field and in the laboratory. Samples of Incoming water (IN), superficial water, deep drainage (LIS), and groundwater (Pz) were taken according to the following methods: (IN) from a tap within the FIA plot; (LIS) utilizing three disk lysimeters positioned beneath the PTS; (Pz) from the piezometers with a pump after purging. The sampling procedure at each measuring point always included an initial purging phase to remove the water accumulated within the measurement device (disk or piezometer) followed by the collection of freshwater samples. Field measurements of pH, redox potential, dissolved oxygen, and temperature were conducted using a flow-through cell and electrodes on the sampled water. The analytic

determinations of NO_3^- , PO_4^- , HCO_3^- , Cl^- , CO_3^- , SO_4^- , NO_2^- , Na, Mg, K, Ca, NH_4^+ , Fe, B, and of other elements such as As, Mn, Al, Cu, Hg, Pb, Zn, Cd, Cr were performed in the laboratory using High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) standards methods and Inductively Coupled Plasma-Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS). Isotopes (^{15}N and ^{18}O in NO_3^-) were also determined. Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD_5), Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) and Suspended Solids (SST) parameters were detected only on IN samples.

2.4 Emission of greenhouse gases (GHG) monitoring

Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions within the FIA system were monitored from September to November 2023 using a Closed Automatic Chamber technique (Parkin and Venterea, 2010; Smith et al., 2010). For this purpose, a network of 8 PVC collars 0.2 m high and 0.3 m in diameter were inserted into the recharge trenches, and one collar was anchored to the ground (outside the trench). During sampling, the PVC chambers were closed over the collars. Air samples of 30 mL were taken from the chamber using a 60 mL polyethylene syringe and were injected into 12 mL pre-evacuated vials (12 mL Soda Glass Vials – Flat Bottomed 739 W, Labco Exetainer®, UK) at intervals of 0, 10, 20, 30 minutes after chamber closure. Concentrations of carbon dioxide (CO_2), nitrous oxide (N_2O), and methane (CH_4), in air samples were analysed using a gas chromatograph and respectively gas fluxes were calculated according to the linear or non-linear increase of gas concentration over time within the chamber headspace following the methodology outlined by Hutchinson and Mosier (1981).

3. Results and discussions

3.1 NO_3^- concentration

After an initial adaptation phase during June 2023, comparing the NO_3^- concentration in the incoming flow (IN) to that of water extracted by the lysimeters from below the PTS (LIS), showed a significant reduction of NO_3^- and reached a maximum of 80% reduction in July 2023 (Figure 2a). However, regarding the piezometers, it appeared that only Pz2 and Pz3 benefited from the recharge effect (see Figure 2b). In fact, from July 2023 NO_3^- concentration exhibited a decreasing trend until October 2023 where it reached a minimum of 1.23 and 7.14 mg L^{-1} for Pz1 and Pz2, respectively. On the other hand, Pz1, Pz4 and Pz5 exhibit NO_3^- concentration similar to the supplied water, suggesting that the water quality was less affected by recharge. In effect, these piezometers were situated on the border of the FIA plot and, probably, these piezometers didn't fully receive decontaminated water from the trenches due to the different groundwater flow in the unsaturated and saturated zones of the aquifer (see Figure 1). Moreover, the sixth piezometer, Pz6, showed negligible nitrate concentration. This can be likely attributed to its positioning within a patch of poplar trees, facilitating natural denitrification processes.

The PTS has demonstrated effective NO_3^- removal from groundwater, with almost complete removal observed at the bottom of the trenches. However, the duration of the denitrifying action of the PTS, and its replacement over time by the mitigating action of plant root systems, will need further evaluation. Therefore, there is a need to enhance the groundwater monitoring network within the FIA system to better understand and address these variations.

Fig. 2 - NO_3^- concentrations at the bottom of the trench (LIS) (a); inside the aquifer (Pz) (b).

3.2 CH₄, CO₂, and N₂O emissions

Fig. 3 - From the left to the right: gas emission of CH₄, CO₂ and N₂O from the FIA system.

Until November 2023 three measurements of CH₄, CO₂ and N₂O fluxes were conducted. Results showed that the emission rates of N₂O and CO₂ can be considered acceptable, as they were one to two orders of magnitude lower than those observed by Pulina et al. (2018) on maize-cultivated soils in Arborea. Contrarily, CH₄ emissions were significant during the initial two monitoring dates but became almost negligible in the third monitoring period (see Figure 3). Moreover, these results are still preliminary for a comprehensive understanding of emissions in the FIA site, and they should be monitored for a longer period.

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, the FIA systems hold promise as an NBS for the decontamination of aquifers polluted by NO₃⁻. The PTS implemented within the FIA has shown effectiveness in promoting denitrification processes, thereby enhancing groundwater quality. Furthermore, the study highlights the importance of enhancing the monitoring network due to the high spatial and temporal variability observed in the dynamics involved. From a hydrological perspective, the system demonstrated an infiltration of 10 m³ h⁻¹ during the experimentation period. It will be essential to evaluate how this infiltration rate may be affected over time by potential clogging-related effects.

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